

Factors Affecting the Developing Speed and Sustainability of Night-Time Economic Services in Bac Giang Province

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ABSTRACT: Until 2030, the province of Bac Giang will focus on promoting the comprehensive development of all economic sectors, with the industrial sector as the main driving force and the service sector as the motivating force. The expansion of concentrated industrial zones, coupled with the formation of new cities, has been a premise that fosters urbanization. These areas attract an abundant workforce of young immigrants and create conditions for the middle class to grow rapidly. That, along with the province's orientation to develop tourism as an important economic sector, Bac Giang has the advantages and potentials to strongly promote night-time service economy. This article analyzes factors that influence the economic growth of night-time service activities in Bac Giang, establishes a basis for well-planned investment, as well as rapid and sustainable development of the service industry.

KEYWORD: Bac Giang, EFA, Night-time economy, Vietnam.

I. INTRODUCTION

This research utilizes exploratory factor analysis (EFA) to analyze the factors affecting the development of night-time economic services in Bac Giang through a regression model with the dependent variable being "Development of the night-time economic services in Bac Giang" and independent variables being: Infrastructure and public utility services; employee safety; human resources; policies; the involvement of the local community; destination management. Conclusions can be drawn about each factor's level of influence, providing effective and sustainable approaches for developing the night-time service economy in Bac Giang.

II. RESEARCH MODEL AND METHODOLOGY

In this study, the authors conducted a survey through a questionnaire to collect primary data. In addition, the author has researched a number of published scientific articles to serve the research process. For primary data collection, the author used a questionnaire paper and conducted a random survey of people in Bac Giang with the number of questionnaires distributed being 315, the number of valid answers collected being 230. According to Hair et al (2014), the minimum sample size to use EFA is 50, preferably 100 or more. The ratio of the number of samples to one analytic variable is at least 5:1, with the number of variables in the factor analysis model of this study being 35 variables, the number of samples needs to be at least 175, so with a sample of 230 is perfectly suitable for the analysis according to the EFA model.

Observations are included in the questionnaire on a 5-point Likert scale, in which, "1" is "strongly disagree"; "2" means "disagree", "3" means "no opinion", "4" means "agree" and "5" means "strongly agree". The proposed research model includes 6 factors and uses the Likert scale to consider the rating. For the selection of factors, the author uses the expert method, in which the experts have many studies in the fields of economics and services. The research model is shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Model of factors affecting the development of night-time economic services in Bac Giang.

The dependent variable of the selected model is “Development of night-time economic services” which is measured by 7 observed variables: (1) Ensuring economic efficiency and competitiveness for enterprises; (2). Maximize visitor contributions; (3). Create jobs and raise income levels; (4) Maintain and enhance quality of life; (5) Contributing to preserving cultural values, craft villages, manners and customs of local people; (6) Contribute to the efficient use of resources; (7) Contributing to the conservation of natural resources. The independent variables are: (1) Infrastructure and public utilities (including 12 observed variables); (2) Safety for workers (including 8 observed variables); (3) Human resources (including 5 observed variables); (4) Policy (including 3 observed variables); (5) Participation of local communities (including 3 observed variables); (6) Destination management (including 4 observed variables).

III. RESEARCH RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

1. Test the reliability of the measure using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient:

Cronbach's Alpha test is a test to analyze and evaluate the reliability of the measure. The purpose of this test is to find out if the observed variables have the same measure for a concept to be measured. The value of more or less contribution is analyzed through the correlation coefficient of the total variable (Corrected Item - Total Correlation), thereby allowing to eliminate inappropriate variables in the research model.

Evaluation criteria: Observable variables with a variable-to-total correlation coefficient (Item - Total Correlation) less than 0.3 will be eliminated and the standard for choosing a measure when Cronbach's Alpha > 0.6 (Hoang Trong & Chu Nguyen Mong Ngoc, 2000).

The results of Cronbach's Alpha analysis for the factors are summarized in the following table:

Table 1: Test of reliability by Cronbach's Alpha for factors

Factor	Observed variables	Symbol	Corrected item – Total Correlation	Cronbach' s Alpha if item deleted	Cronbach's Alpha
INFRASTRUCTURE AND UTILITY SERVICES	Infrastructure for traffic at night	INFRAST 1	0.613	0.525	0.721
	Public street lighting system.	INFRAST 2	0.624	0.538	
	Public toilet system	INFRAST 3	0.652	0.653	
	Communication systems	INFRAST 4	0.631	0.817	

	Camera surveillance system	INFRAS 5	0.672	0.812	
	Software systems for managing, reporting incidents, hotspots on smart mobile devices	INFRAS 6	0.671	0.815	
	Access to transport	INFRAS 7	0.615	0.826	
	Waste treatment systems	INFRAS 8	0.598	0.829	
	Access to medical services, health care	INFRAS 9	0.603	0.828	
	Entertainment facilities	INFRAS 10	0.785	0.886	
	Catering establishments	INFRAS 11	0.792	0.888	
	Shopping facilities	INFRAS 12	0.765	0.890	
SAFETY FOR THE COMMUNITY	Impact of noise on local people's health	SFTC 1	0.754	0.662	0.865
	Regulations relating to noise.	SFTC 2	0.771	0.658	
	Regulations on the use of wine, beer or other alcoholic beverages	SFTC 3	0.626	0.684	
	Security and social order for residents and visitors and other troubles for residents (theft, fights, gambling, prostitution, drugs...)	SFTC 4	0.817	0.852	
	Air quality (dust and odor of exhaust gases)	SFTC 5	0.851	0.843	
	Informing businesses about the laws related to participating in night-time economic activities	SFTC 6	0.830	0.869	
	Informing and warning residents and visitors about the risk of crime	SFTC 7	0.819	0.811	
	Preserving and promoting local spiritual and cultural life	SFTC 8	0.830	0.812	
HUMAN RESOURCES	Appropriate qualification	HR 1	0.557	0.646	0.624
	of a foreign language	HR 2	0.623	0.722	
	Good communication skills	HR 3	0.562	0.845	
	Good problem-solving skills	HR 4	0.676	0.682	
	Good moral qualities	HR 5	0.857	0.795	
POLICY	Create strategic plan for night-time economic development	P1	0.856	0.639	0.830
	Develop regulations related to night-time economic activities	P2	0.786	0.587	
	Providing subsidy packages for businesses to promote night-time economic activities in Bac Giang	P3	0.830	0.554	

PARTICIPATION OF LOCAL COMMUNITY	Local people are friendly and hospitable	PLC1	0.523	0.801	0.521
	Locals help tourists	PLC2	0.486	0.784	
	Local people are conscious of protecting the environment and developing local tourism	PLC3	0.564	0.795	
DESTINATION MANAGEMENT	Protect and preserve the environment	DM 1	0.690	0.815	0.748
	Ensuring security and social order	DM 2	0.777	0.732	
	Ensure the safety of food, life and property for visitors	DM 3	0.695	0.817	
	Receive and properly handle complaints from visitors	DM 4	0.801	0.801	

Source: Research team compiled from survey results

The results of testing the reliability of the factors show that most of the proposed factors have good reliability, Cronbach's Alpha values are all greater than 0.6. Particularly, the factor of the participation of local communities in the development has Cronbach's Alpha coefficient = 0.521, according to Hair et al (2014), although the reliability of this factor is not high, it is acceptable. All variables have Item - Total Correlation > 0.3 so all variables are kept.

2. EFA exploratory factor analysis for independent variables

The results of exploratory factor analysis EFA show that the test results are relatively good. KMO coefficient = 0.852 > 0.5, so the use of this data set for factor analysis is appropriate (Kaiser, 1974). Bartlett's Test is used to see if the observed variables in the factor are correlated, this value is also achieved when the Sig value of the test = 0.000 < 0.5, so the observed variables are relevant and were eligible for factor analysis by EFA (table 2).

Table 2: Results of KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.852
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	14135.922
	df	923
	Sig.	0.000

Source: Analysis of survey data by the research team

The breakpoint of factor analysis is set on the basis of the Eigenvalue coefficient, the maximum number of factors is selected when this coefficient has the smallest value > 1 and the cumulative percentage is greater than 50%. With the above conditions, there are 6 factors extracted at Initial Eigenvalues of 2.069 > 1, the total variance extracted is 62.822% > 50%, showing that 6 factors extracted in EFA reflect 62.8220% of the difference. Variations of all measures are included in the model.

Table 3: Summary of exploratory factor analysis results for independent variables

Rotated Component Matrix ^a									
	Component								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
INFRAS1	0.690								
INFRAS2	0.670								
INFRAS3	0.667								

INFRAS4	0.690								
INFRAS5	0.738								
INFRAS6	0.728								
INFRAS7	0.690								
INFRAS8	0.670								
INFRAS9	0.765								
INFRAS10	0.759								
INFRAS11	0.739								
INFRAS12	0.859								
SFTC1		0.903							
SFTC2		0.885							
SFTC3		0.882							
SFTC4		0.871							
SFTC5		0.809							
SFTC6		0.739							
SFTC7		0.843							
SFTC8		0.885							
HR1			0.861						
HR 2			0.851						
HR3			0.851						
HR4			0.790						
HR5			0.778						
P1				0.894					
P2				0.863					
P3				0.847					
PLC1					0.777				
PLC2					0.761				
PLC3					0.735				
DM1						0.827			
DM2						0.819			
DM3						0.617			
DM4						0.805			
Initial Eigenvalues	7.081	4.936	3.157	2.699	2.394	2.069			
Variance extracted	16.093	11.280	7.174	6.133	5.440	4.702			
Total variance explained	16.093	27.373	34.547	40.680	46.120	62.822			
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.									
a. Rotation converged in 6 iterations.									

Source: Analysis of survey data by the research team

Considering the rotation matrix table, with Varimax rotation and only the Factor Loading factor loading factors > 0.3 (table 3), all observed variables with load factors > 0.5 are considered significant. real meaning (Hair et al., 2014), so all these observed variables are kept for later analysis.

The final results of factor analysis exploring the measures of independent variables including 35 observed variables are loaded with 6 factors, the order and names of the factors are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4: Summary of factors affecting the rapid and sustainable development of the night-time economy after exploratory factor analysis EFA

TT	Factor name	Symbol	Observed number
1	Infrastructure and public utility service	INFRAST	12
2	Safety for the community	SFTC	8
3	Human resource	HR	5
4	Policy	P	3
5	Participation of local community	PLC	3
6	Destination management	DM	4
	Total		35

Source: Compiled from the research team's analysis of survey data

3. EFA exploratory factor analysis for dependent variable

The results of the first EFA discovery factor analysis for the dependent variable, a quick look at the Rotated Component Matrix table shows that the dependent variable does not converge on one factor. There are 2 factors extracted, in which there is a problem in the observed variables NTED1; NTED2; NTED 7 is uploaded in two groups of variables 1 and 2. At the same time, the variable NTED7 does not download the desired factor at all.

Review the variable-total correlation in the reliability test Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of the measure of economic development = 0.341 > 0.3, however, the coefficient of correlation of this variable - total is quite low compared to other variables in the factor of night-time economic services development. So the author decided to remove the variable NTED7 and run the EFA a second time.

The results of running EFA for the second time after removing the variable NTED7 show that the test results are relatively good. KMO coefficient = 0.89 > 0.5, so it is appropriate to use this data set for factor analysis (Kaiser, 1974). Bartlett's Test also passes when the Sig value of the test = 0.000 < 0.5, so the observed variables are related to each other and are eligible for factor analysis by EFA (table 5).

Table 5: Results of KMO and Bartlett's Test for the variable Night-time economic service development

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		0.890
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	3280.130
	df	50
	Sig.	0.000

Source: Analysis of the author's survey data

The coefficient Initial Eigenvalues = 5.214 > 1 proves that the extracted factor in Table 5 is representative of the variation with uniform information. The total variance extracted is 58.235% > 50%, which proves that the factor extracted in EFA reflects 58.235% of the variation of all measures included in the model.

Table 6: Summary of EFA exploratory factor analysis results for the dependent variable

Symbol	Factor
	1
NTED2	0.792
NTED6	0.763

NTED4	0.742
NTED5	0.735
NTED1	0.732
NTED3	0.724
Initial Eigenvalues	5.214
Total variance explained	58.235
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.	
a. 1 components extracted.	

Source: Analysis of survey data by the research team

Combining the results of testing the reliability of the measure (Cronbach's Alpha) and exploratory factor analysis (EFA), the study has identified factors, variables and measures that can be used to evaluate the factors. affecting the rapid and sustainable development of the night-time economy of Bac Giang province.

4. Regression analysis of factors affecting night-time economic development in Bac Giang province

To test the research hypotheses, the author performed multiple linear regression of 6 variables of 6 factors proposed in the adjusted research model after qualitative research. The selection method is Enter and the regression results are as follows:

Table 7: Coefficient of regression model

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	0.751a	0.624	0.653	0.38221	1.792
a. Predictors: (Constant), IFRAST, SFTC, HR, P, PLC, DM					
b. Dependent Variable: NTED					

The result of the regression model synthesis coefficient in Table 2.13 for adjusted R² (Adjusted R Square) = 0.653 means, with the sample size of the research model of 85, there is 65.3% variation of the dependent boundary (Night economy development) is due to the influence of 6 variables included in the above research model. The rest, 34.7% is influenced by factors other than the research model. Statistical value Durbin-Watson = 1.792 < 3, shows that the model has no autocorrelation, therefore, the quality of regression can be considered as good.

Table 8: Coefficient of Variance

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	91,765	6	8.230	58.321	0.000b
	Residual	72,971	426	.142		
	Total	164,930	432			
a. Dependent Variable: NTED						
a. Predictors: (Constant), INFRAS, STFC, HR, P, PLC, DM						

Source: Analysis of survey data by the research team

Table 8 gives test results F = 58.321 and Sig value = 0.000, proving that the proposed research model is consistent with the surveyed data set.

Table 9: Result of multiple linear regression coefficient

Coefficients ^a							
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	-0.213	0.233		0.246		
	INFRAST	0.254	0.029	0.231	0.000	0.801	1.148
	SFTC	0.324	0.033	0.328	0.000	0.849	1.128
	HR	0.132	0.022	0.186	0.000	0.780	1.183
	P	0.213	0.019	0.220	0.000	0.764	1.212
	PLC	0.121	0.020	0.103	0.021	0.778	1.223
	DM	0.146	0.026	0.150	0.000	0.621	1.021

Source: Analysis of survey data by the research team

The results of the study in Table 9 show that the acceptance coefficient (Tolerance) is quite high (from 0.621 to 0.849), and at the same time, the variance exaggeration coefficient VIF is low (from 1.021 to 1.223, less than 2). Therefore, it can be concluded that the relationship between these independent variables is not significant, it can be considered that there is no multicollinearity phenomenon in the model.

From the above results, it is possible to draw a multiple linear regression equation representing the relationship between the factors affecting the rapid and sustainable development of the night-time economic services in Bac Giang province as follows:

$$NTED = 0.231*INFRAST + 0.328*SFTC + 0.186*HR + 0.121*PLC + 0.150*DM$$

With a sample size of 230 and a study in Bac Giang province, the regression results show that, among the groups of factors included in the study, the group SAFETY FOR THE COMMUNITY has the strongest impact on night-time economic services development. The standardized Beta coefficient = 0.328 is significant in the condition that other factors are constant, if changing 1 unit for the variable SFTC, the average change in NTED will be 0.328 units. Similarly, the variable INFRASTRUCTURE AND PUBLIC UTILITY SERVICES (INFRAST) has the second strongest influence on night-time economic services development in Bac Giang (normalized Beta = 0.231) and human resources (standardized beta factor = 0.186). The group of factors that have a lower impact on the rapid and sustainable development of the night-time economic services in Bac Giang is: PARTICIPATION OF THE LOCAL COMMUNITY IN NIGHT ECONOMY DEVELOPMENT with a standardized Beta coefficient of 0.121.

IV. CONCLUSION

With the aforementioned analysis results, it can be seen that elements having a profound impact on the night-time economic service development in Bac Giang are the "Employee safety" and "Infrastructure and public utility services". Accordingly, the issues that the local administration and people of Bac Giang province need to pay attention to, for the developing speed and sustainability of the night-time service economy here include: Infrastructure such as traffic systems, lighting, sanitation system, information technology system, entertainment system, food chains and shopping facilities; safety for the community such as noise reduction, alcohol use regulations, security and order, air quality, warning of crime risks, conservation and promotion of spiritual life for people. This study is also an important basis for Bac Giang province to implement new policies to support and promote the rapid and sustainable night-time economic service development.

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